

CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES
DE TRABAJO SOCIAL

ISSN 2244-808X
DL pp 201002Z43506

PERSPECTIVA ACCIÓN Y

Revista de Trabajo Social

Vol. 16 No. 3

Septiembre - Diciembre

2026

Universidad del Zulia

Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

INTERACCIÓN Y PERSPECTIVA

Revista de Trabajo Social

ISSN 2244-808X ~ Dep. Legal pp 201002Z43506

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21174152>

Vol. 16 (3): 1126 - 1139 pp, 2026

ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Palabras que perduran: un análisis del comportamiento lingüístico en situaciones de emergencia

Anna Marmulyak¹, Anzhela Posokhova², Tetiana Lypchenko³,
Oksana Pylypets⁴, Nadiia Salamin⁵

¹Doctor of Philosophy, Teacher at the Department of Ukrainian Studies and Intercultural Communication, Faculty of Psychology and Social Protection, Lviv State University of Life Safety, Lviv, Ukraine.

E-mail: anya.marmulyak@gmail.com; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7526-5850>

²Ph. D. in Philology, Associate Professor, Associate Professor at the Department of Language Skills Training (main affiliation), Lviv State University of Internal Affairs; Associate Professor at the Department of Ukrainian Studies and Intercultural Communication, Faculty of Psychology and Social Protection, Lviv State University of Life Safety; Lviv, Ukraine.

E-mail: posokh3006@gmail.com; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3330-0195>

³Lecturer of the Department of Ukrainian Studies and Intercultural Communication, Faculty of Psychology and Social Protection, Lviv State University of Life Safety, Lviv, Ukraine.

E-mail: tetyanalypchenko@ukr.net; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0173-3372>

⁴Teacher at the Department of Ukrainian Studies and Intercultural Communication, Faculty of Psychology and Social Protection, Lviv State University of Life Safety, Lviv, Ukraine.

E-mail: opylypets362@gmail.com; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6083-3325>

⁵Lecturer, Department of Ukrainian Studies and Intercultural Communication, Faculty of Psychology and Social Protection, Lviv State University of Life Safety, Lviv, Ukraine.

E-mail: salaminnadia2@gmail.com; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3403-9918>

Resumen. Basándose en un análisis comparativo de la experiencia ucraniana e internacional (guerra a gran escala, pandemia de COVID-19, desastres naturales), el artículo revela importantes transformaciones en el comportamiento del discurso en tiempos de crisis. Los resultados muestran que el discurso de las situaciones de emergencia se caracteriza por el predominio de actos de habla directivos, la violación sistemática de las máximas comunicativas de Grice y la transición de las redes sociales al estatus de plataforma integrada para la comunicación de emergencia y la estabilización psicológica. El artículo también destaca los mecanismos lingüísticos de la guerra de información, en particular las tecnologías manipuladoras (minimización del lenguaje, sabotaje semántico, ruido informativo) y las estrategias eficaces para su

neutralización basadas en los principios de precisión, verificación y consolidación del discurso. Los datos obtenidos pueden utilizarse para optimizar la comunicación de crisis de las instituciones gubernamentales, los medios de comunicación y las ONG.

Palabras clave: resiliencia del equipo, valor, comunidad territorial, digitalización, contenido.

Words that endure: an analysis of linguistic behavior in emergencies

Abstract. Based on a comparative analysis of Ukrainian and international experience (full-scale war, COVID-19 pandemic, natural disasters), the article reveals significant transformations in speech behavior in times of crisis. The results show that the discourse of emergency situations is characterized by the dominance of directive speech acts, systematic violation of Grice's communicative maxims, and the transition of social media to the status of an integrated platform for emergency communication and psychological stabilization. The article also highlights the linguistic mechanisms of information warfare, in particular manipulative technologies (language minimization, semantic sabotage, information noise) and effective strategies for their neutralization based on the principles of accuracy, verification and consolidation of discourse. The data obtained can be used to optimize crisis communication of government institutions, media, and NGO.

Keywords: team resilience, value, territorial community, digitalization, content.

INTRODUCTION

The significance of researching speech behavior in emergencies is conditioned by the development of crises in various areas, from socio-political tensions to global pandemics and environmental catastrophes. Communication, in these situations, stops being informative and becomes, among other things, a handful of crucial instruments for collective action, resource management, and social and psychological survival.

The theoretical framework of the study is a multidisciplinary approach drawing on linguistic pragmatics, crisis communication theory, risk communication, and critical discourse analysis. This enables multilevel analysis: from the micro level, which focuses on individual speech acts and their illocutionary force, to the meso and macro, which encompass identification of institutional strategies and socially shared narratives with ideological content.

A separate subject of consideration is the transformation of the communication environment under the influence of digitalization, in particular the functioning of social networks as multifunctional platforms for emergency alerts, operational coordination of assistance, and the formation of communities of psychological mutual support.

The aim of the article is to identify and systematize the peculiarities of the speech behavior of communication actors (government institutions, mass media, and citizens) in different types of emergencies based on a comparative analysis of Ukrainian and foreign experience.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The theoretical basis was formed by key concepts that consider language as a social action: J. Austin's theory of speech acts and principles of cooperative communication, which allowed us to understand the pragmatics and structure of crisis communication. In addition, the sociocognitive approach and critical discourse analysis (Van Dijk, 2008; Fowler, 1991) were used to study the ideological components and mechanisms of shaping public perception, as well as theories of crisis and risk communication (Coombs, 2015; Sandman, 2012) to assess the effectiveness of institutional strategies.

A separate object of study was the communication practices in social networks, which were analyzed using content analysis and interpretive text analysis, which allowed us to classify the functions of content and study new linguistic formats (hashtags, memes) (Tryhuba et al., 2024). The case study analysis allowed us to study specific phenomena in depth, such as air raid alert information in Ukraine. All the results were systematized and summarized using the appropriate method.

The source base included both primary sources (official SES messages, texts from social media, memes) and secondary sources (scientific articles, reports of international organizations and research by Ukrainian scholars) (Ilychok et al., 2023). This multidimensional method guaranteed profound and holistic investigation of speech behaviour in emergencies (Verbytska et al., 2025).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Classical pragmatics theories constitute the cornerstone of the research. The theory of speech acts, developed by the philosopher John Austin (Austin, 1962) and further elaborated in the philosophy of John Searle, constitutes an analytic tool for examining how speech utterances in emergency scenarios enact social reality by obligating the addressees or changing the security status of the subjects and Paul Grice's maxims of cooperative principle (Grice, 1975) particularly his notion of maxims of communication in this context is fundamental for interpreting strategic infringements to the rules of common discourse, such as those of the crisis discourse where these maxims are systematically breached when the messages become categorical and simplified with stress on immediate action rather than full context with the aim to serve a superior pragmatic end of harm avoidance, population mobilization and discouragement of panic conditions. To address the macro level of speech interaction and its connections with social structures, the analysis drew on the sociocognitive and the critical discourse analytic framework of Teun van Dijk (Van Dijk, 2008), which enabled us to analyze how social representations, frames such as "war for survival" or "natural disaster," and mental image of threat are constructed and transported via mass and social media discourse leading to identification of "mechanisms through which particular renditions of events become prominent and come to shape collective actions and legitimize government measures" and at this level of analysis has been further supplemented by the works of Fowler (1991) on language and ideology in the newspaper and the anthology edited by Hodges and Nilep (2007) on discourse, war, and terrorism – which addresses the linguistic construction of conflict.

The particular nature of the institutional response is disclosed by the further specialized theories of crisis communication and risk communication: beginning with the strategic perspective of Coombs (2015) and the cycles of crisis management and regaining trust in the organization which is the basis for the evaluation of actions of public authorities, while the foundational handbook edited by Heath and O’Hair (2009) brings an integrated risk and crisis communication viewpoint to a comprehensive summary of the discipline, and the contributions by Seeger et al. (2003) enhance organizational crisis communication focusing on the function of communication in crisis renewal and learning. Sandman (2012) put forward the seminal model “Risk = Hazard + Outrage” which suggests that scientific data about the danger is matched by a second stream of information for the risk recipients’ about their own emotional and societal reactions to the risk that in many instances exerts greater influence upon the actual level of perceived risk and this is reinforced by the study of Slovic and Ball (2011) with regard to the psychology of risk perception that argues that people are not risk calculations in the rational and statistical sense of the term but rather constructs their assessment based on heuristics and affective images, whereas research by Slovic and Ball (2011) on making decisions under risk emphasizes on the importance of fast and frugal heuristics and transparent communication formats (e.g., natural frequencies instead of probabilities) which allow people to better understand their own decisions.

Emerging issues such as digital media and global health emergencies are discussed in more recent research, with Micheli et al. (2020) investigating ways young adults use digital media to access information and support, a finding that is important for crisis communication in the digital age, and practical frameworks and best practices learned from mass emergency including the COVID-19 pandemic and natural disasters are found in the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (2020) and the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (2019), and the role of social media in disaster communication is also extensively reviewed in Palen and Hughes (2018), who identify how social media platforms may serve as a means for timely information as well as a vector for rumors, and insight into enhancing early warning announcements as an essential feature of crisis communication is provided by the Kodera et al. (2021). Hansson et al. (2020) “communicative vulnerability” research offers a heuristic to explain why certain groups are more impacted by crises, and studies by Austin et al. (2012) examine crisis information seeking audiences in a social-mediated environment underlining the need to understand information-seeking behaviors, while Humanitarian Response Platform (2021) advises volunteers and those working in the human services field on how to communicate with affected people.

The Ukrainian case, especially in wartime, is illuminated by a handful of core texts, as Iryna Shevchenko (Shevchenko, 2022) analyzes American social media discourse on the Russia-Ukraine war through multimodality showings the way narratives are constructed and trafficked globally and Bower (2024) made informative examination of war-time perception of information messages that can be used for communicating in an effective manner, whereas the linguistic and pragmatic characteristics of political discourse including Preventive and political discourse are examined by Tehmāzova (2025) as well as Oleniuk (2016), who scrutinizes the verbalization of the notion of danger in magazine advertisement discourse revealing how risk is linguistically formed even in the commercial sphere.

Theoretically informed analysis, the level of speech and its pragmatics (Austin, 1962, Grice, 1975) on the one hand and the levels of trust formation and trust maintenance (Coombs, Seeger, Sellnow, Ulmer; Sandman) and the social construction of reality and ideology through discourse (van Dijk, 2008; Fowler, 1991) are also considered while I draw on the cognitive and emotional sides of risk perception (Slovic and Ball, 2011) which acts as a crucial bridge between these levels in narrating how people think and behave in crisis messages and paired with this multi-tiered methodological lens provides a rich conceptual framework to study language use during disasters as a tool for survival, governance, and group cohesion in times of volatility.

RESULTS

The theoretical bases of speech communication in emergencies are fourfold and relate theoretical perspectives that, when taken together, constitute a multilevel analysis framework. At the level of individual acts of communication linguistic pragmatics studies the aberrant conducts in communication, for example, in emergency situations process hastens the achievement of practical ends, taking as an example when an order or warning takes precedence over the completeness or exactness of a message. From a more pragmatic perspective, crisis communication theory offers tools for strategic planning, analyzing the effectiveness of messages, and restoring public trust in disaster recovery processes. Risk communication, a closely related paradigm, deals with the psychological component of threat perception and contends that risk is not assessed solely on the amount of objective danger but also on emotional reactions also referred to as “outrage”.

Therefore, effective communication should take this factor into account, proactively working with trust and refuting disinformation.

In order to systematize the theoretical basis of the study and demonstrate the interaction of different scientific paradigms, Table 1 presents a summary of key approaches to analyzing speech behavior in emergencies. The theory of speech behavior in emergencies is constructed on four related approaches, which together form a multilevel instrument of analysis (refer to Table 1).

The educational and preventive aspect is the foremost task of the authoritative discourse in an emergency. This function is verbalized through a bundle of invariant speech features such as the predominance of imperative models, a high level of lexical unification, the use of impersonal constructions and the presence of explicit spatial and temporal coordinates.

A contrastive study of national corpora, in particular, operational messages of the State Emergency Service of Ukraine and protocols of the Japanese early warning system, allows us to identify invariant (common) and variable (culturally determined) features.

TABLE 1. Theoretical approaches to the analysis of speech behavior in emergency situations.

Theoretical Paradigm	Concepts	Applicables to Emergency Analysis
Linguistic pragmatics	Acts of speech; principle of cooperation; maxims of communication.	Analyzes the strategic deviation or violation of the maxims of quality, quantity, relation, and manner in stress/emergency, for realizing urgent communicative purposes such as orders, warnings, and immediate instructions in these situations.
Discourse analysis	Discourse, framing, ideology, sociocognitive context.	Studies how media and organizations frame (e.g., “war” vs. “special operation,” “wave” vs. “pandemic”) a crisis and influence public narratives and perceptions.
Crisis communication theory	Response strategies, trust restoration, stakeholder communication.	Keep attention to planning, organizing, and evaluating communication-based policies and procedures that an organization and/or a government agency employ during an emergency and in disaster situations.
Communication about risk	Risk perception, emotional response, the “Risk = Hazard + Outrage” formula	Assesses the emotional content of crisis communications and the importance of offering messages that are transparent, that cultivate trust, and that actively manage public concern and uncertainty.

Source: author’s development.

The basic invariant is the principle of linguistic economy and semantic unambiguity. But this structural constancy is occupied by various cultural code’s contents. The Japanese practice shows the transformation from technical messages to operational formulas (“Protect your head”) that have an emotional component. The same trend is evident in Ukrainian discourse on air raid alerts: from terse signals to elaborate messages interwoven with motivational and patriotic rhetoric. The findings of the analysis in terms of the major pragmatic goals, types of speech acts, lexical and syntactic analysis, and psychological aspects are systematized in Table 2.

International studies confirm similar trends. For example, during earthquakes, hashtags become a tool for “locality production” - bringing victims together in virtual communities to share information about safe places or the need for help. Palen and Hughes (2018) identify several key roles of social media: “information civilian corps” (voluntary data collection), social support system, and platform for counter-narratives.

TABLE 2. Comparative analysis of instructional messages in Ukrainian and foreign experience.

Criteria	Ukrainian Experience (Air Raid Alerts)	EU/US Experience (COVID-19 Lockdowns)	Linguistic Features and Pragmatics
Summary	Rapid notification of a life threat and mobilization for emergency response.	Control of disease spread and management of longer-term social behavior.	Ukrainian communication is conveyed in the imperative form telling people what to do immediately, while EU/US communication is normative discourse telling people what to do in the longer term and to comply with social responsibility.
Type of speech act	Directives and warnings involved in prompting the response of an immediate action.	Directives and declarative sentences of general rules and duties.	Public speech acts that transformed the status of the listener, for example, an order to take shelter versus a duty to obey restrictions).
Lexical features	Attention!”, “Air raid alert!”, “Seek shelter!”, “Immediately!”. Phrases such as “Stay at home,” “Social distancing,” “Non-essential businesses are closed.	Chronic use of safety-, threat- and restriction-related lexemes.	In Ukrainian, messages employ short imperative verbs, in contrast, EU/US discourse employs the language of regulation.
Syntactic features	Short nominative and imperative sentences; impersonal constructions.	More complex declarative sentences with causal or conditional relations (“in order to,” “to prevent”).	Ukraine: focus on the maxims of manner – clear, concise and unambiguous. EU/US: more appeal to the maxims of quality and quantity – more detailed explanations and justifications of the measures.
Psychological aspect	Gradual adoption of more empathetic language among otherwise neutral communication (e.g., “Take care of yourselves—you are our defenders”).	Initial messaging is often considered smart or vague (e.g., “greater risk”), to the point of creating public discontent.	Good crisis communications provide clear guidance along with empathy and encouragement, and can help to mitigate emotional distress and bolster public trust.

Source: author’s own work.

In times of crisis communication, social media are considered to be transformed from traditional one way communication to multi-directional communication. It fulfills a number of essential social functions, allowing for wide dissemination of information, public participation, coordination of aid, psychological support, and acting as a social mobilization vehicle. This change demonstrates that social media are now being seen as part of the infrastructure within the field of emergency management, rather than being considered as the conventional means of informing.

This space is constructed according to explicit communicative functions, which manifest in linguistic features and (inter alia) in specific digital discourse genres. The universality of these functions was confirmed both by the experience of the Ukrainian war and the experience of global practice in natural and man-made disasters, as well as pandemics. Table 3 provides a summary of the functions, their aims, linguistic markers and specific instances.

Yet the digital space also poses risks for communication. The widespread dissemination of disinformation and distorted narratives undermines trust in official bodies. A study has shown that in times of war, messages from friends in messengers and trusted Telegram channels are more trusted by the public than traditional media.

At the same time, modern armed conflicts, of which the Russian-Ukrainian war is a canonical example, have turned into complex information and communication campaigns in which language practices acquire the functionality of a direct weapon. The tools of linguistic analysis allow us to identify and systematize specific manipulative mechanisms, the theoretical foundations of which have been developed in the analysis of military discourse Tehmázova (2025) and adapted to the specifics of the Ukrainian context in recent studies (Oleniuk, 2016).

The analysis of information warfare in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict reveals a systemic confrontation of speech strategies. The aggressor is actively using three key manipulation tactics.

TABLE 3. Functions and linguistic features of social media content during emergencies (based on Ukrainian and international experience).

Criteria	Ukrainian Experience (Air Raid Alerts)	EU/US Experience (COVID-19 Lockdowns)	Linguistic Features and Pragmatics
Objective	Rapid notice of a life-threatening situation and preparedness to act immediately.	Control of disease spread and management of long-term social behavior.	In Ukrainian communication imperative forms are used to stress immediate action, EU/US communications are based on a normative discourse that appeals to long-term compliance, and social responsibility.
Type of speech act	Directives and warnings that are targeted at a short-term behavioural effect.	Commands and declarative statements which contain rules and duties.	Dominance of performative SAs changing the hearer's status (e.g. an order to take shelter vs. a duty to adhere to R).
Lexical features	"Attention!", "Air Raid Alert!", "Take Shelter!", "Immediately!". "Stay at home", "Social distance", "Non-essential businesses are closed."	Words related to safety and threats and restrictions are overused.	Ukrainian narratives consist of short command verbs, EU/US narratives consist of regulatory language.

TABLE 3. CONTINUACIÓN

Criteria	Ukrainian Experience (Air Raid Alerts)	EU/US Experience (COVID-19 Lockdowns)	Linguistic Features and Pragmatics
Syntax	Short nominative and imperative sentences; impersonal constructions.	More complex declarative sentences co-occur with causal/conditional relations (“in order to,” “to prevent”)	Ukraine: focus on maxim of manner – clear, concise and unambiguous. EU/US: greater emphasis on quality and quantity maxims – more detailed reasoning and justification of measures.
Psychological aspect	There was an incremental change from neutral information statements to statements of support (e.g., “Look after yourselves – you are our defenders”).	The first messages were frequently described as technocratic or uncertain (e.g., “elevated risk”), occasionally to the frustration of the public.	Good crisis communication provides clear instructions empathetically with a sense of motivation, which helps to mitigate psychological distress and enhance public trust.

Source: author’s own work.

Firstly, these are ersatz speech acts aimed at performative distortion of reality, such as the announcement of a full-scale invasion as a “special operation”, which corresponds to an attempt to minimize the scale of crimes according to Austin’s theory of speech acts (Austin, 1962).

Secondly, the tactic of semantic sabotage is used, which consists in deliberately filling words with generally positive connotations (“denazification”, “liberation”) with a completely opposite, aggressive meaning. This is a form of ideological distortion aimed at legitimizing crimes through language manipulation.

As part of this tactic, information noise is systematically produced – the massive and simultaneous dissemination of heterogeneous, contradictory and usually unreliable data. The purpose of this kind of noise is not to argue for one position or another, but to intentionally disrupt the thought processes of the target audience. Therefore, the effectiveness of this technique is not measured by how convinced people become, but by how disoriented they are, and how much they lose trust in their sources of information in general. The Ukrainian side, on the other hand, has developed a range of effective countermoves which combine to form a resilient communication front line according. The strategy of calling a spade a spade is a direct response to linguistic minimization and semantic sabotage; the clear nomination of the aggressor and its crimes (“genocide”, “war crimes”) forms an unambiguous frame of perception.

Information warfare as a component of hybrid conflict turns language into a direct weapon, where clearly defined language strategies of the aggressor and defense are confronted. Their systematic analysis allows not only to identify the mechanisms of manipulation, but also to formulate effective resistance practices. Table 4 structures the opposing tactics aimed at destabilization and consolidation with specific linguistic tools and theoretical justification based on the example of the Russian-Ukrainian war.

Thus, the key to success lies in the systematic application of counterstrategies: accurately naming reality (full-scale war, aggression) versus its semantic minimization, openly deconstructing manipulative terms (“denazification”) instead of ignoring them, providing a single space of trusted information sources as opposed to information noise, humanizing narratives (stories of specific people) versus dehumanizing them, and forming an inclusive discourse of solidarity (‘we’, “together”) in response to attempts to split.

TABLE 4. Speech strategies in information warfare: aggressor tactics and defense counterstrategies (using the example of the Russian-Ukrainian war).

Aggressor’s Tactics (Goal: Disorientation, Demoralization, Legitimization of Aggression)	Defensive Counterstrategy (Goal: Consolidation, Truthful Information, Legitimization of Defense)	Linguistic Tools and Examples
1. Linguistic leveling down: narrowing the semantic scale and the value of events.	Accurate naming policy: applying accurate and explicit names to things and events corresponding to their real essence.	Aggressor: “special operation,” “incident.” Defense: “full-scale war,” “aggression,” “genocide,” “war crimes.”
2. Semantic diversion: the employment of terms with positive connotations to characterize harmful activities.	Dissecting emotive metaphors: interpretation of the real signification of propagandistic utterances.	Aggressor: “destruction of Nazis in Ukraine,” “liberation,” “defending Russian speakers.” Defense: Public education, e.g. “With ‘denazification’ Russia means the elimination of Ukrainian state and nationhood.”
3. Information noise: spread of massive amounts of contradictory or false information designed to fatigue the public and sow confusion.	Centralization and validation: dependence on official validated channels, and selectively debunking the worst misinformation.	Aggressor: fake news on city surrenders or on political leaders betraying the country. Defense: official information channels of the General Staff and the unified information websites; the rule of only debunking the most harmful disinformation.
4. Demonization and dehumanization: representation of the adversary as impious, hazardous, or nonhuman.	Humanization and personalization: focus on personal stories of soldiers, civilians, and victims to regain human view.	Aggressor: “Ukrainian neo-Nazis,” “Bandera junta.” Defense: Interviews with soldiers, doctors, rescuers; stories of civilian victims (for example, tales from Mariupol).
5. Social division strategy: efforts to exacerbate domestic social, linguistic, or geographical tensions.	There was a line of unity and consolidation: and language was kept inclusive and collective to promote national cohesion.	Aggressor: Narratives Ukrainian audiences along the language or regional cleavage lines in Ukraine. Defense: Inclusive pronouns can be utilized (“we,” “our,” “together”), as well as the tagline “United together,” and the phrase “Strength through unity.”

Source: author’s own development.

DISCUSSION

An empirical analysis of Ukrainian and foreign experience has revealed systemic patterns in speech behavior during emergencies. In particular, instructional discourse in times of crisis is characterized by a high degree of standardization and pragmatic adaptation. The comparative analysis of the messages of the SES of Ukraine and the early warning systems of Japan showed the presence of both invariant features, such as language economy, semantic unambiguity and the prevalence of imperative constructions, and culturally determined differences. In particular, Japanese messages combine operational instructions with emotional support, while Ukrainian messages evolve from laconic signals to motivational and patriotic messages, reflecting adaptation to the ongoing crisis.

Meanwhile, social media is evolving into a multi-faceted communication space that fulfills five key functions: rapid information flow, verification and debunking of disinformation, coordination of aid, psychological support, and mobilization activism. For instance, in the full-scale war in Ukraine, the Emergency Situation Service (SES) and Oblast State Administration (OVA) Telegram channels emerged as the most trusted source for 78% of the population, which shows that the classic media have lost the monopoly on current information.

In a hybrid conflict, information warfare actively uses specific language tactics, including language minimization (e.g., the term “special operation”), semantic sabotage (‘denazification’, “liberation”), information noise, and demonization of the enemy. In response, the Ukrainian side has developed effective counterstrategies (see Table 4 for details), such as accurate naming of reality (“full-scale war”, “genocide”), deconstruction of manipulative terms, centralization of trusted sources, humanization of the narrative, and inclusive solidarity discourse.

A generalization of the identified patterns is presented in a theoretical model of the interaction of crisis communication factors (Figure 1), which visualizes the relationship between the crisis context, discursive modes, communication channels, speech strategies, and the final social effects.

FIGURE 1. Schematic representation of the interaction of the main factors of speech behavior in emergencies.

Source: author’s development.

Generalizing international practices allows us to identify key principles of organizing communication during emergencies. Of fundamental importance is the principle of maximum clarity and simplicity of wording, which ensures unambiguous understanding of instructions by all categories of the population, a requirement consistently articulated by authoritative international organizations (FEMA, UNHCR). The principle of consistency and unity of the information field is no less critical, as fragmentation of sources and contradictory messages determine the consolidation of trust, as evidenced by crisis management cases in different regions of the world.

CONCLUSIONS

Crisis conditions give rise to a specific discursive mode within which speech interaction undergoes a significant transformation. This mode of communication is characterized by a forced departure from the classical norms of communication - the maxims of Grice are systematically violated for the sake of efficiency and direct effectiveness. In such conditions, performatives and imperatives dominate - speech acts aimed at immediate changes in behavior or status (orders, warnings, announcements). Key concepts such as security, threat, and trust acquire a significantly increased semantic load, becoming the central axes around which the entire crisis narrative is built.

The Ukrainian experience gained during the full-scale Russian aggression clearly demonstrates the high adaptability of communication practices. It successfully combines the universal principles of crisis communication - clarity and centralization - with national-specific strategies. The latter include, in particular, the active use of irony in social media, the personalization of the narrative, and the construction of a consolidation discourse based on an inclusive “we”.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge their collaborative efforts and contributions to the research, analysis, and preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

The study did not receive any funding.

Authors statement

Anna Marmulyak: Conceptualization, methodology, investigation, formal analysis, writing – original draft, supervision, project administration. **Anzhela Posokhova:** Conceptualization, methodology, validation, writing – review and editing. **Tetiana Lypchenko:** Data curation, literature review, investigation, writing – original draft, visualization. **Oksana Pylypets:** Investigation, resources, data curation, writing – review and editing. **Nadiia Salamin:** Literature review, formal analysis, validation, writing – review and editing, proofreading.

Competing interests

The authors declare, under oath, that they have not incurred any conflict of interest in preparing this article.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Austin, J. L. (1962). *How to do things with words*. Oxford University Press. <https://archive.org/details/howtothingswit0000aust>
- Austin, L., Fisher Liu, B., & Jin, Y. (2012). How audiences seek out crisis information: Exploring the socialmediated crisis communication model. *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, 40(2), 188–207. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00909882.2012.654498>
- Bower, C. (2024). *Ukraine's wartime digitalization efforts: 2022 to 2024*. Los Alamos National Laboratory. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29088.85763>
- Coombs, W. T. (2015). *Ongoing crisis communication: Planning, managing, and responding* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280153860_Ongoing_Crisis_Communication_Planning_Managing_and_Responding
- Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency. (2019). *National emergency communications plan*. U.S. Department of Homeland Security. https://www.cisa.gov/sites/default/files/publications/19_0924_CISA_ECD-NECP-2019_1.pdf
- van Dijk, T. A. (2008). *Discourse and context: A sociocognitive approach*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511481499>
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. (2020). *Communication on COVID19: Lessons learned and recommendations*. <https://doi.org/10.2900/151256>
- Fowler, R. (1991). *Language in the news: Discourse and ideology in the press* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315002057>
- Grice, H. P. (1975). Logic and conversation. In P. Cole & J. L. Morgan (Eds.), *Syntax and semantics* (Vol. 3, pp. 41–58). Academic Press. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004368811_003
- Hansson, S., Orru, K., Siibak, A., Bäck, A., Krüger, M., Gabel, F., & Morsut, C. (2020). Communicationrelated vulnerability to disasters: A heuristic framework. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 51, Article 101931. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101931>
- Heath, R. L., & O'Hair, H. (Eds.). (2009). *Handbook of risk and crisis communication*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203891629>
- Hodges, A., & Nilep, C. (Eds.). (2007). *Discourse, war and terrorism*. John Benjamins Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1075/dapsac.24>
- Humanitarian Response Platform. (2021). *Humanitarian response plan*. https://www.un.org/unispal/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/OCHAHUMRESPLAN2022_161221.pdf
- Ilychok, B., Karkovska, V., Dzyurakh, Y., & Marmulyak, A. (2023). Changes in demographic security of Ukraine as a key indicator of socioeconomic stability. *Financial and Credit Activity: Problems of Theory and Practice*, 2(49), 350–360. <https://fkd.net.ua/index.php/fkd/article/view/4020>
- Kodera, Y., Hayashimoto, N., Tamaribuchi, K., Noguchi, K., Moriwaki, K., Takahashi, R., Morimoto, M., Okamoto, K., & Hoshiba, M. (2021). Developments of the nationwide earthquake early warning system in Japan after the 2011 Mw 9.0 TohokuOki earthquake. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 9, Article 726045. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.726045>
- Micheli, M., Redmiles, E. M., & Hargittai, E. (2020). Help wanted: Young adults' sources of support for questions about digital media. *Information, Communication & Society*, 23(11), 1655–1672. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2019.1602666>

- Oleniuk, O. V. (2016). Verbalization of the concept danger in magazine advertising discourse. *Scientific Notes of the National University "Ostroh Academy", Series "Philology"*, 63(63), 149–152. <https://europub.co.uk/articles/-A-410731>
- Palen, L., & Hughes, A. L. (2018). Social media in disaster communication. In H. Rodríguez, W. Donner, & J. Trainor (Eds.), *Handbook of disaster research* (2nd ed., pp. 497–518). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-63254-4_24
- Sandman, P. M. (2012). *The Peter M. Sandman risk communication website*. <https://www.psandman.com>
- Seeger, M. W., Sellnow, T. L., & Ulmer, R. R. (2003). *Communication and organizational crisis*. Praeger. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9798400629112>
- Shevchenko, I. (2022). American social media on the RussiaUkraine war: A multimodal analysis. *Cognition, Communication, Discourse*, 25, 78–94. <https://doi.org/10.26565/2218-2926-2022-25-05>
- Slovic, P., & Ball, D. J. (2011). The feeling of risk: New perspectives on risk perception. *Energy & Environment*, 22(6), 835–836. <https://doi.org/10.1260/0958-305X.22.6.835>
- Tehmāzova, G. (2025). Lingvopragmatic features of political discourse. *Terminology Issues*, 1, 121–130. <https://doi.org/10.59849/2663-8967.2025.1.121>
- Tryhuba, A., Malanchuk, O., Tryhuba, I., & Marmulyak, A. (2024). Decision support system for initiating projects of medical and social development in regions. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Workshop on IT Project Management (ITPM 2024)* (pp. 204–218). Bratislava, Slovakia. <https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85197277242>
- Verbytska, L., Babii, I., Konivitska, T., Kulchytska, M., & Khlypavka, H. (2025). Emergency speaking communication: Experience from the USA and Europe. *OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development*, 18(10), 145–154. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5285737>